

Constructing Emancipation: How Can Ethnomusicology Help?

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Abstract. The paper reflects on emancipation and the possible role of ethnomusicology to achieve it. Starting from the assumption that politicization is fundamental to people's emancipation, first, the paper offers a close look at recent Brazilian political facts, revealing the depoliticization project in progress and how it interferes on the emancipation issue in the country. The second part of the paper presents a critical perspective on paths to emancipation. I present my ethnographic work on rap music in the periphery of Rio de Janeiro, more specifically the rap workshops for young peripherals in schools, as an example that offers a perspective of emancipation along with ethnomusicology. Then, I argue about the potential inscribed in the engaged approaches in ethnomusicology and how must be the core of these approaches to constructing emancipation. In conclusion, the essay argues that we need to establish a critical political thought to reach our aim for human emancipation to improve this society fundamentally unequal owing to the inequality between social classes, race, and gender.

Introduction

Emancipation is an important step to our awareness of the world. It is a complex process that puts us as an active individual into the historical process. It is something that we must seek, and which we must trigger other people to seek too. Therefore, this paper aims to discuss the topic of emancipation from an ethnomusicological perspective and how we, as ethnomusicologists, can contribute to the construction of emancipation in our society.

The analysis in this paper was undertaken in 2019 in Brazil, with Brazilian political crisis in the background. A more in-depth analysis of the Brazilian crisis of this period can be found in Perry Anderson's book *Brazil Apart: 1964-2019* (2019), which provides a critical review of Brazilian governments from 1964 to the year 2019. However, I would like to highlight in this article three recent events in Brazilian history that help to understand the situation I encountered during my fieldwork.

In 2016, the country had just suffered the ousting of the president, considered as a political coup. Right after that, the government that came into office began a phase of attacks on labor rights, contribution time for retirement, and its benefits. Cuts in education investments in the country has also increased. In the year 2018, the murder of the Afro-Brazilian politician and city councilor of Rio de Janeiro, Marielle Franco, by militias,¹ shocked the whole country as well as

1. Militias are organizations formed primarily by police, military firemen, and prison guards—active or retired—who began to dominate territories previously controlled by narco-traffickers with the justification of “liberating” the local population in exchange for a “protection” fee.

the world. In the same year, a far-right presidential candidate won the elections, spreading fake news on online social media.

This chaotic background leads us to several questions, especially for me as a Brazilian and a researcher in the country. But the overall question here is “how”: How did we let all this happen? How did we get here? There are people among the dominant classes in Brazil who are pleased with this current situation. However, most people in the country suffer from the neoliberal reforms.² Therefore, the passivity of the Brazilians and the depoliticization –that is, politics without politics (Dean, 2009)–, during the events in the years 2016-2019 is something to think about alongside the topic of emancipation.

This paper is a result of engaged research that holds the musician as an “organic intellectual” (Gramsci, 2001) – that is, as an intellectual who uses and shares knowledge for the people. Based on readings by Gramsci (2000; 2001) and Paulo Freire (2005; 2017), emancipation is understood here as a weapon against bourgeois class hegemony. Bearing this in mind, this paper seeks to analyze artistic interventions carried out by the rapper Nyl MC and DJ Pirigo in a public school in the *Maré’s favela*, in Rio de Janeiro, with 11- to 13-year-old students. These interventions put into practice the concept of the organic intellectual by trying to build a way towards emancipation on a local level.

Drawing on the analysis of rap workshops in a public school in Rio de Janeiro, I intend to debate the practice of the theoretical discussion about emancipation. The approach is structured as a dialogue, following the *Musicultura’s* methodological perspective of participatory action research. The *Musicultura* is a research group composed of university and public-school teachers, and undergraduate, graduate, and high school students. Its actuation is based on interdisciplinary references, assuring the diversity of its participants who, besides distinct academic levels, are from diverse areas of knowledge, class, and color. Through guidance on the *Musicultura Maré* group’s, Gramsci’s, and Freire’s ideas, this article considers emancipation based on rap workshops in a public school in a micro-perspective, and the observations and analysis made in Brazilian territory during the years 2018 and 2019 in a macro-perspective.

2. The term neoliberal is used here to refer to the fundamentalist ideas of the market and free trade applied after the 1970s, which increase social inequalities and run counter to the concern for a society of equal opportunity. The application of neoliberal policies in a country of the global south functions as a renewal of the domination that already existed between metropolis and colony at the time of classical liberalism. We can also use the term ultraliberalism to define the liberalism of our times (Anderson, 1995; Miranda 2020). According to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics - IBGE (Portuguese acronym), Brazil had almost 52 million people in poverty and 13 million in extreme poverty in 2019. For more information: <https://g1.globo.com/jornal-nacional/noticia/2020/11/12/ibge-brasil-tem-quase-52-milhoes-de-pessoas-na-pobreza-e-13-milhoes-na-extrema-pobreza.ghtml>.

Theorization of the current depoliticization scenario in Brazil

Under the recent events in Brazil, we can affirm that the country is having a critical political time. In critical moments, the people usually revolt against the oppression, and it was not different in Brazil. A portion of the people took to the streets; Brazilians shouted: “no coup!”; they prayed for murdered councilwoman Marielle Franco; they tried to stop the extreme right-wing expansion. But it all happened anyway, suggesting that the critical moment may not have begun in 2016 with the impeachment of President Dilma Rousseff. The gap between the people and emancipation is biggest now, but it is not by chance. How Brazil got to this place is important in thinking about emancipation.

First, I intend to briefly discuss those events, beginning with the latest one, the election of extreme right-wing candidate, Jair Bolsonaro, in October 2018. The scenario in the run-up to the election was complicated. Former President Lula was arrested in a process full of proven legal errors,³ and was therefore prevented from standing as a candidate in elections that year. The left was focused on which candidate was best prepared to defeat Bolsonaro and not which candidate had the best government proposal that could match each voter.

Bolsonaro had the most promising possibility of winning the elections since the world scenario tended towards the extreme right, especially with the election of Trump in the United States in 2016. In addition, the bourgeoisie and liberals of Brazil saw in Bolsonaro the possibility of gaining more economic advantages. For sociologist Sabrina Fernandes (2019), the Brazilian bourgeoisie was exchanging the support it received from the previous right and center-left governments for total subordination from the new government.

Before the elections, the other relevant event in the recent history of the country was the tragic death of Marielle Franco in March 2018. Franco was a left-wing Brazilian politician who fought for human rights in Rio de Janeiro. Her murder is linked to militias. Zaluar & Conceição (2007) show that militias are expanding, both in the occupied territories and in Brazilian politics, especially in the politics of Rio de Janeiro.

There are several facts linking the Bolsonaro family to the militias. One of those accused of killing councilwoman Marielle Franco, Adriano Nóbrega, is pointed out as a beneficiary of an illegal money-laundering scheme run by Jair Bolsonaro’s eldest son, Flávio Bolsonaro, during his term as state representative for Rio de Janeiro.⁴ In addition, there is the involvement of Flávio’s former advisor, Fabrício Queiroz, with the militias and the homage made by Flávio Bolsonaro at

3. For more information: <https://theintercept.com/2019/06/09/brazil-car-wash-prosecutors-workers-party-lula/>.

4. For more information: <https://theintercept.com/2019/03/18/jair-bolsonaro-family-militias-gangs-brazil/>.

the request of his father, Jair Bolsonaro, to Adriano Nóbrega during his term as a state representative.⁵

Before the murder of Marielle became an issue in international media, Brazilian politics appeared in news around the world with the impeachment of the then president, Dilma Rousseff, in 2016. Rousseff's impeachment was considered a coup by several jurists, leading to the creation of a manifesto in defense of the Democratic and Constitutional State of Law in Brazil, signed by more than 8 thousand jurists and intellectuals.⁶

From 2003 to 2016, the country was governed by the center leftist party called "Workers' Party" (*Partido dos Trabalhadores*) represented by the abbreviation "PT". Lula ruled two four-year terms while Dilma Rousseff one and a half four-year terms. After the loss of popularity of the government and the intensive collaboration of the Brazilian media to promote the "Car Wash Operation" (*Operação Lava a Jato*) against the corruption of the PT, the leader of the lower house of deputies, Eduardo Cunha, who had just broken with the government, opened a case accusing Rousseff of "budget maneuvering." But the same maneuver had been made by former presidents and was being undertaken by 17 state governments with current mandates. Rousseff is not a defendant in any lawsuit, and none of her opponents has evidence to accuse her of corruption. Geraldo Prado, jurist and professor of procedural law at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, said: "There is no fiscal fraud, there is no proof whatsoever of a crime of responsibility, there is no causality between economic crisis, credit decrees and the Crop Plan"⁷ (the decrees of budget supplementation or in the transfers of the Crop Plan were the bases of the accusation against the president).

Alysson Mascaro (2018) recalls that the first term of the Lula administration already faced difficulties with lack of congressional support and accusations of corruption. For the author, the 2016 crisis is only an extreme amplification of the contradictions that the PT governments have relied on to govern. Several reactionary measures were sanctioned by the interim government of Michael Temer. However, as Sabrina Fernandes (2019) recalls, the reactionary measures during the interim government after the coup did not start there. During the Rousseff administration, the proposals of loss of rights applied in the Temer government were already passing through Congress.⁸ Furthermore, President Rousseff herself sanctioned the

5. For more information: <https://noticias.uol.com.br/politica/ultimas-noticias/2020/02/15/bolsonaro-condecoracao-miliciano-morto-ba.htm>.

6. Manifesto in full: https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B25Hqzc_ozMGRXQ3Y0IyVnRGM2M/view?resourcekey=0-VAyaI7GUZWMqXpNnK6-bNQ.

7. Official website of the National Senate: <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/materias/2016/05/03/presidente-dilma-nao-cometeu-qualquer-crime-que-justifique-o-impeachment-afirmam-juristas>.

8. The main reform established by the Temer government was the Proposal of Constitutional Amendment, known as PEC 241 or PEC 55, which creates a ceiling for public spending for up to 20 years. The proposal would prevent public investment in key areas such as health, safety, and education to reduce inequality in the country. During Rousseff's government projects of fiscal adjustments were already circulating in Congress. More information in:

Antiterrorism Law that criminalized social movements in Brazil after large demonstrations in June 2013.

The June 2013 protests are also a major political event in the country's recent history. But it was also not there that the critical political moment in Brazil began. Fernandes points out that the June protests are just another "morbid symptom facilitated by the very weakness of the idea and the materiality of democracy in Brazil"⁹ (Fernandes, 2019, p. 114). Therefore, what we have in Brazil is a systemic problem.

Florestan Fernandes ([1968] 2008, [1973] 2009) describes Brazilian capitalism as less compatible with human rights than capitalism in other countries. He posits that the Brazilian elite has no interest in constituting autonomy in relation to the international market. Thus, it continues to share its profits with the hegemonic bourgeoisie, maintaining their dependence. In this action, the over-exploitation of workers and those condemned to unemployment is maintained and expanded. The underdevelopment of the country keeps it stagnant in this restricted democracy that encourages popular non-participation and maintains archaic remnants of the era of Brazil-colony, as Sabrina Fernandes (2019) agrees. The greatest example that Florestan Fernandes presents is of the Black Brazilians, who achieved freedom from slavery but were never really integrated into society. They were forced, for the most part, to live on the margins of society due to structural racism.

Developing the concepts of post-politics and ultra-politics

This information allows us to see that social problems, political crises, and non-participation of the people are a project of Brazilian capitalism. Sabrina Fernandes (2019) points out a depoliticization process in the country. Depoliticization is not necessarily the denial of politics, but rather the poor ability to analyze and criticize the current conjuncture (Fernandes, 2019; Dean, 2009). It is fomented by the right and by part of the left: the right promotes anti-communist myths as a way of depoliticization, while the left –the "Workers' Party" in Brazil– denies alternatives and utopias for a social-based development, demanding "sacrifices" for social development, and proposing class conciliation. To better explain the depoliticization process in Brazil, Fernandes uses the concepts of post-politics and ultra-politics. In her words, post-politics

[...] acts in the realm of common sense as a form of post-ideology, wherein matters related to political, social, and economic status are effectively managed, rather than struggled for, without the

<https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/materias/2016/12/28/aprovacao-da-pec-do-teto-mostra-apoio-do-congresso-ao-ajuste-fiscal>.

9. In the source: "sintoma mórbido facilitado pela própria fraqueza da ideia e da materialidade da democracia no Brasil." Translation by the author.

influence of ideological positions; that is, the making of politics becomes subordinated to a presumed impartiality attributed to technocracy and enlightened specialists (Fernandes, 2017, p. 154).

Summarizing in a few words, post-politics is the false idea about an alleged impartiality. It is disguised by post-ideology, as neutral, technical know-how, and ethical, and tries to portray the social problems as a simple issue of management, and not as political issues that must be disputed. On the other hand, the ultra-politics concept offers another guidance.

The most well-known definition of ultra-politics is provided by Slavoj Žižek in a general footnote in *The Ticklish Subject*: "Ultra-politics has recourse to the model of warfare, politics is conceived as a form of social warfare, as the relationship to 'Them', to an Enemy" (Žižek, 1999, p. 241) [...] Ultra-political conflict is militarized in the sense that it constructs the identity of an Enemy and promotes it as the core of the social and political relations. [...] Unlike class antagonism, ultra-political warfare is waged against a constructed Enemy, but as depoliticization it ends up reinforcing the hegemonic state of things (Fernandes, 2017, p. 206).

Ultra-politics is used to empower those who are already benefited by the status quo, framing themselves as victims and struggling for conservative moralism to avoid losing their ruling status. Therefore, it is created a manipulative radicalization, "them against us." And if you are not engaged in the war against the "Enemy" (in the terms set by ultra-politics), then you must be the "Enemy." This is depoliticization because it removes critical thought. It removes the complexity of the political situation by offering simplistic and false answers. And, as we can see, depoliticization does not necessarily mean the total rejection of the political space.

Depoliticization, in fact, can occur with a very politicized appearance, as it does in Brazil. The ultra-political and the post-political operate in different ways, but they are two sides of the same coin of depoliticization. And depoliticization affects the possibility of becoming involved politically.

Attacks on social rights and depoliticization are not something particular to Brazil. Latin America in general is very unstable politically, and throughout the world, fascist ideologies and extreme-right candidates seek opportunities. Here it is worth briefly defining what fascism is, because fascism is chameleonic and parasitic, using various ideologies, if necessary, for the march toward power. As such, its dynamics are characterized by a mixture of political ideas, no matter whether these ideas are contradictory or not, and by essentially authoritarian governance.

The concept of fascism is cited in three ways in history and literature, as we can see in the readings of Umberto Eco (1995) in the article "Ur- Fascism," Walter Lauquer in the book *Fascism: Past, Present, Future* (1997), and Eric J. Hobsbawm in *The Age of Extremes* (1994).¹⁰ The first associates fascism only with its birth in Italy, even though there are other similar

10. This text was read in its Portuguese translation, *A era dos extremos*, from 1995.

dictatorial regimes. The second holds that in addition to the Italian example, the German Nazi regime would be equally fascist. The third believes that all movements or regimes that share a common basis with Italian fascism – ideological similarities, organizational criteria, and political objectives – can be called "fascist."

Although the term is used in different ways by different people, we can state that fascism is an authoritarian regime of domination based on a sense of decadence and on the affirmation of the existence of a national crisis, for which it argues that there is no solution that can be achieved through traditional means. Thus, fascism offers a monopoly of political representation exercised by a single mass political party which, in its structure, is established hierarchically. In it, an ideology is founded where a single leader alone is able to lead and rebuild national values, exalting national collectivity, relying on the values of liberal individualism, but also using communal ideas when convenient. It establishes as an ideal the collaboration of classes in a corporatist way, leaving them stagnant, thus translating into a counter-revolutionary regime that despises class struggle.

Currently, fascist ideology is gaining ground in world politics, but there is also a considerable amount of struggle against it. In short, some current events: in 2019 Bolivia suffered a political-military coup and in Chile a series of protests were initiated in response to the lack of social rights in the country, remnants of the Chilean military dictatorship (1973- 1990). However, in 2020 we saw the Bolivian people reelect the party ousted from power in Bolivia and in Chile there was a massive vote for a new constitution. The presidential election of Donald Trump in 2016 inspired the political right across the world. Trump was the symbol of the rise of the extreme right in the world. We can see in European parties an increase of anti-immigrant agendas, in the Philippines a persecution of human rights defenders, and others. Nonetheless, in 2020, Trump lost his reelection as president and there was an uprising of anti-racist protests in the United States. The events in the USA, Bolivia, and Chile give hope that popular alternatives can be born.

Paths to emancipation: the organic intellectual of rap

In order for popular alternatives to be born, emancipation must be stimulated. Emancipation can be defined as a political practice related to the struggle to overcome oppression and domination (Freire, 2005). While depoliticization keeps people as an object and not as a subject, politicization can contribute to changing reality, and can lead to emancipation. In the Gramscian view, "politicization entails the unification of theoretical and practical consciousness" (Gramsci, 2000, p. 333). In this sense, Gramsci (2001) understands that the intellectual plays an important role in this emancipation process. Gramsci distinguishes between traditional intellectuals and organic intellectuals. The traditional intellectuals reproduce hegemonic ideas and organic intellectuals have the function of revealing the ruling class domination and developing the

“good sense” —the “good sense” that the working class already have in their daily practice, buried under several layers of “common sense,” as synthesized by Michael Burawoy (2010) when describing the people's consciousness and the role of the organic intellectual.

Therefore, the organic intellectual confronts the common sense produced and reproduced under hegemony, bringing questioning and a critical position to the society. Thus, the role of these intellectuals is organizational, educational, and directive (Gramsci, 2000, p. 25). The organic intellectual – who does not necessarily consist of a single person but can be a group or an organization – is recognized here as a contributor toward popular emancipation.

In this direction, I used Gramsci's concept in my research to analyze the underground scene of hip-hop in Rio de Janeiro with my interlocutors Nyl MC and DJ Pirigo. Nyl was born and raised in the Irajá neighborhood, a lower and lower-middle class suburb located in the North Zone of the city of Rio de Janeiro, where he lives to this day. He started rapping in 2007 with the group BDO MC's (short for oppression gang, in Portuguese: "*Bonde da Opressão*"). He pursued a solo career in 2009. He is also a cultural producer and, together with the collective *Resistência Cultural* (Cultural Resistance), has worked to get several artists – new or already established – to perform in the North Zone of the city.

DJ Pirigo has been DJing since he was 14, when he was part of the BGK collective in the Penha neighborhood of Rio de Janeiro. Pirigo and Nyl met precisely because Nyl worked as a cultural producer bringing artists to perform in public spaces in the North Zone. Admiring each other's work, they decided to work together.

It is apparent that Rio de Janeiro's underground hip-hop scene is located in the city, both spatially and in terms of class and race. In a statement for the documentary “O Som do Tempo” (The Sound of Time), made by rapper and researcher Arthur Moura, the members of the rap group Sons of the Ghetto reported that while middle-class youth were organizing at universities, the youth from the periphery were organizing in the hip-hop movement. This statement speaks volumes about the class and racial division that exists in Rio de Janeiro, as in Brazil, and about the importance of Rio de Janeiro's hip-hop scene for the critical organization of youth from the periphery – with the teaching of self-organization to resist socially and culturally.

Nyl experiences the daily routine of Rio de Janeiro's periphery and establishes dialogues with several popular musical styles in the city. The reflection he brings about the social and political conditions is highly relevant to building a critique of that reality. He shares this reflection in his music and on stage with the part of the population that is most oppressed by the system of inequality. Gramsci maintains that intellectual practice must unite theory and practice, and Nyl achieves this in his rap music.

The idea of the organic rap intellectual does not begin with my research. Rogério Silva (2012), in his doctoral thesis on rapper Mano Brown of the group Racionais' MC as an organic intellectual of the periphery, points out how the hip-hop movement proved to be efficient in transforming the lives of several young people from the peripheries of several Brazilian cities. To do so, he analyzes the trajectory of rapper Mano Brown, leader of the rap group Racionais MC's in the 1990s. Silva's work has been echoed outside the academy, making me think about how the Gramscian idea of the intellectual could make sense in some way in the musical artistic world.

For the authors Silva (2012) and Tiarajú Pablo D'Andrea (2013), the influence of Racionais' lyrics influenced the political action of people from the periphery, creating an understanding for those people of how the peripheries are understood by public power and disseminated by the media, and influencing the self-image of the periphery residents themselves, bringing a sense of peripheral collectivity and class consciousness. Alongside Racionais' MC, MV Bill, Planet Hemp, Marcelo D2, Gabriel O Pensador, Black Alien, and MC Marechal have marked the Brazilian hip-hop scene by raising a systemic criticism in their lyrics.

The idea of praxis linked to the concept of the organic intellectual encouraged us to produce actions with rap aimed at emancipation. In 2019, Nyl MC, DJ Pirigo, and I started to hold rap workshops at the public school where I teach as a music teacher in the Maré slum in Rio de Janeiro. In the workshops, Nyl MC and DJ Pirigo taught about the history of hip-hop and its relationship with the Black population, but the focus of the workshop was to encourage students to think critically. We encouraged the students to express their criticism in a creative and interactive way, through rap music composed by themselves.

The rap workshop took place with the fifth and sixth grade classes. The children in these classes are usually between 10 and 13 years old. The funk carioca is the music genre the students hear most commonly, however, they were also familiar with rap music, and the two musical styles converge on each other. Because they already had some acquaintance with rap music, the questions they first asked Nyl and Pirigo were of a more personal nature, for example, how long Nyl and Pirigo had been performing as a rapper and DJ, their ages, and their Instagram and YouTube accounts.

Nyl started the rap workshop by defining what rap and hip-hop are. He made an analogy to a tree and its fruit, wherein the tree represents hip-hop, and the fruits represent its elements (break dance, rap, DJing, and graffiti). Still using the metaphor of the tree, he pointed out that this tree is not alone, it is among many other trees (other musical styles) in a forest (which would be the world of music). He taught knowledge about rap and hip-hop in a playful way, also showing that music styles do not exist in isolation but rather among many styles.

Nyl and Pirigo highlighted the Afro-cultural background of hip-hop, framing it as an Afro-diasporic style. What he tried to point out, in the end, is that Africa and its cultures play an

important role not only in the hip-hop movement, but also in other aspects of our lives as diasporic people.

After this first introductory part, Nyl performed some of his songs for the students. They really enjoyed this part and were visibly excited while watching the show. As soon as Nyl finished his performance, he and Pirigo began to provoke the students into producing their own rhymes. They organized themselves into 4 or 5 groups, consisting of 3 or 6 people, and started writing verses to perform. First, we suggested that the students write rap lyrics about themes that they had raised during their interaction with us, but then we and the students agreed that it was better to write about that year's school theme: peace and violence.

The dialogue with students was spontaneous, but they were ecstatic about the situation. They saw Nyl MC as an artist who took some time in his agenda to meet them. This activity lasted two class periods for each class, each period lasting 50 minutes, that is, in total we had 1 hour and 40 minutes of workshop for each class. There were four classes in total.

It is worth mentioning that the students did not believe that the workshop would happen. Before the event, after I told them a little about the rappers' musical careers, they said that "no one wants to go to the Maré slum." The lack of self-esteem for living in a favela area had already been discussed in the classroom with these students. At the time, the situation was extreme. We commented on the issue of a state helicopter opening fire on the school's outskirts in the middle of our class hours. I asked in one of the affected classes if they thought that the governor's son was also going through this. They answered "no." I asked if they thought it was fair. They answered that they were in a slum and the government's son did not live in the slum. I asked why there is this difference between those who live in the slum and those who don't. There were a few seconds of silence until one student said that there should be no difference in treatment. The other students agreed with her. Although they could not explain why there was such a difference in treatment between "slum dwellers" and "non slum dwellers," they knew that there was a difference. This "embryonic critical awareness" of domination leads us to Gramsci's theory. According to Burawoy (2010), Gramsci believes that there is a critique being developed by workers and it can be elaborated through the dialogue with intellectuals. Students between the ages of 11 and 13 know that the governor's son was not witness to gunfire at his home or school, and that they are.

There is no doubt that the rap workshop was important for those students, however, we have no way of measuring precisely how much the rap workshops helped in the emancipation process. As Paulo Freire argues on the cover of his book, *Pedagogy of Autonomy*: "Nobody is the subject of anybody's autonomy. On the other hand, nobody matures suddenly, at the age of 25. We mature every day, or not. Autonomy, as the maturation of being for oneself, is a process, it is to come to be." Therefore, what I can say about the rap workshops and the construction of

autonomy is that there was a contribution in some way in the emancipatory process of these children. We offered experiences for them to develop autonomy in different ways and, thus, whether or not they can advance in their emancipatory processes.

These students don't have a normal life. Maré district is a marginalized residential area of Rio de Janeiro that suffers from regular police operations. Police operations are incursions by military police into slum territories. In these operations the rights of the people who live there are not respected. There is no concern about exchanges of fire and the safety of the people there. For Silva & Silva (2012), all the favelas were created as a kind of “deposit” for the social problems of the city: “no housing? No school? Are you Black? Are you poor? Are you unemployed? Are you a former inmate? Irregular construction? Let the favela absorb”¹¹ (Silva & Silva 2012, p. 4).

The state policy of abandoning part of the population allowed the urban disorganization of the city. Consequently, the State lost territorial and social control to armed groups— militias and drug traffickers – which it attempts to regain through armed incursions into the locations or with the strategy of establishing permanent policing. However, Marielle Franco (2014) called attention to the preservation of oppression and violence by the State, whatever tactics it chooses.

Thus, the militarization of urban life in Rio de Janeiro “makes culture military, its values and its procedures, the references in confronting the urban problems in the most varied sectors: security, education, social assistance, cultural and others”¹² (Grupo Musicultura 2015, p. 157). Trying to confront this perspective, the rap workshop created a counter-hegemonic space that encouraged the kids to think critically about the reality, discharged their anguish and fears, and made them realize that their life is not less important than others. We consider such moments of interaction as an important contribution of political movement toward emancipation.

Indeed, rap music can be used as a tool of politicization and consequently emancipation. In a text produced by Nyl MC to share the experience that he had with the students, he summarizes the meaning of the workshops:

“The purpose of the workshops is not to train MCs, but to provide a conversation about cultures of African matrixes with Rap as a common thread, to connect with rhythms of our culture, such as Samba and Funk carioca, and to create a space to experience the making Rap” (Nyl MC, 2020).¹³

11. In the source: “não tem moradia? Não tem escola? É negro? É pobre? É desempregado? É ex-detento? Construção irregular? Deixe que a favela absorva.” Translation by the author.

12. In the source: “Ela faz da cultura militar, seus valores e seus procedimentos, as referências no enfrentamento dos problemas urbanos nos mais variados setores: segurança, educação, assistência social, cultural e outros.” Translation by the author.

13. Translation by the author. Full text in: <https://medium.com/@nyldesousa/na-minha-passagem-pelo-ambiente-escolar-como-estudante-tive-notas-que-pontuaram-dez-o-auge-e-4988ed7fe950>.

Therefore, rap workshops have an emancipatory purpose in their existence, aiming to awaken critics to learn about our Afro-Latin origins and to think about our unequal and violent social context. With the scenario of political instability described in this article, awareness of the Brazilian reality becomes very important so that people are not held hostage to neoliberal solutions that harm the already precarious life of the poor and Black population in Brazil. In this sense, I defend here the importance of an emancipatory agenda guiding ethnomusicological approaches.

Constructing emancipation in ethnomusicology

Constructing emancipation is a complex topic, because there is no formula to follow. What we can do for an emancipatory approach in ethnomusicology is to follow principles. The main principle, I expect from an ethnomusicology committed to the emancipation of people, can be expressed with a statement by the Brazilian critical educator Paulo Freire. For him, “to affirm that men and women are persons and as persons should be free, and yet to do nothing tangible to make this affirmation a reality, is a farce” (Freire, 2005, p. 50).

Therefore, we must seek critical thinking, politicization, and emancipation all the time. However, this should not result in a movement of us researchers trying to free people who are considered “uneducated.” It is a complex process of teaching and learning at the same time between both sides. Freire (2017) says that nobody ignores everything, and nobody knows everything, at the same time we all know something, and we all ignore something. Freire also highlights that “we cannot say that in the process of revolution someone liberates someone else, nor yet that someone liberates himself, but rather that human beings in communion liberate each other” (2005, p. 113).

Gramsci’s and Freire’s thoughts are very similar in my perspective. Freire argues for the role of the educator and Gramsci for that of the organic intellectual, but both value the battle of ideas for emancipation. Thus, to change our reality, we should contribute to this battle. We should seek praxis in our approaches. And to do this, we must place action and reflection interacting with each other as a dialectical unity. The role of critical awareness is to combat the misalignment between thought and practice. Ethnomusicology must aim to overcome the dichotomy in thought and practice to contribute to emancipation. Ethnomusicology is constantly changing because we are active in it.

The conjuncture analysis carried out in this text makes it clear that every action is political. The macro can influence the micropolitical, as the micro can influence the macropolitical on some level. We must not ignore the responsibility we all have to seek to overcome existing oppression and inequality, and to do it we should seek praxis. But the “how” to reach the praxis is a question that must be prioritized. We cannot do this without people. In conclusion,

emancipation is a process involving “the organic self-empowerment of the oppressed through recognition and the will to change (expressed in a ‘collective will’) building together with the organic intellectual representatives of this group” (Fernandes, 2016, p. 494). We should politicize our actions and position ourselves as organic intellectuals. In so doing, we can help to construct emancipation.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, P. (2019). *Brazil Apart: 1964-2019*. Verso.
- Anderson, P. (1995). Balanço do neoliberalismo. *Pós-neoliberalismo: as políticas sociais e o Estado democrático*. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 9-23.
- Burawoy, M. (2010) *O marxismo encontra Bourdieu*. Campinas: Editora da Unicamp.
- d’Andrea, T. P. (2013). *A formação dos sujeitos periféricos: cultura e política na periferia de São Paulo*. (Tese de doutorado em Sociologia, Universidade de São Paulo).
- Dean, J. (2009). Politics without politics. *parallax*, 15(3), 20-36.
- Eco, U. (1995) “Ur-Fascism”, *New York Review of Books*, 22: 12-12.
- Fernandes, F. (2008). *Sociedade de Classes e subdesenvolvimento*. 5ª Edição. São Paulo: Global Editora
- Fernandes, F. (2009). *Capitalismo dependente e classes sociais na América Latina*. 4ª Edição. São Paulo: Global Editora.
- Fernandes, S. (2016). Pedagogia crítica como práxis marxista humanista: perspectiva sobre solidariedade, opressão, e revolução. *Educação & Sociedade*, 37(135), 481-496.
- Fernandes, S. (2017). *Crisis of Praxis: Depoliticization and Leftist Fragmentation in Brazil* (Doctoral dissertation, Carleton University).
- Fernandes, S. (2019). *Sintomas mórbidos: a encruzilhada da esquerda brasileira*. Autonomia Literária.
- Franco, M. (2014) *UPP—A redução da favela a três letras: uma análise da política de segurança pública do Estado do Rio de Janeiro*. (Dissertação de mestrado em Administração, Niterói, Universidade Federal Fluminense).
- Freire, P. (2005). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (30th anniv). New York, NY: Continuum. (Original work published 1970).
- Freire, P. (2017). *A importância do ato de ler em três artigos que se completam* (Vol. 22). Cortez editora.

- Gramsci, A. (2000). *The Antonio Gramsci reader: selected writings, 1916-1935*. (D. Forgacs, Ed.). New York: New York University Press.
- Gramsci, A. (2001) *Cadernos do cárcere (vol. 2)*. Edição e Tradução de Carlos Nelson Coutinho, Coedição de Luiz Sergio Henriques e Marco Aurélio Nogueira. 2ª edição. Rio de Janeiro: Civilização Brasileira.
- Hobsbawm, E. (1995) *Era dos extremos: o breve século XX*. Editora Companhia das Letras.
- Laqueur, W. (1997) *Fascism: Past, present, future*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mascaro, A. L. (2019). *Crise e golpe*. Boitempo Editorial.
- MC, N., 2020. Notas sobre Oficinas de Rap nas Escolas. [Blog] *Medium Nyl MC*, Available at: <https://nyldesousa.medium.com/na-minha-passagem-pelo-ambiente-escolar-como-estudante-tive-notas-que-pontuaram-dez-o-auge-e-4988ed7fe950> (accessed 19.07.2021).
- Miranda, J. E.B. (2020). O ultraliberalismo enquanto categoria conceitual. [Digital publishing platform] *Lavra Palavra*. Available at: <https://lavrapalavra.com/2020/12/02/o-ultraliberalismo-enquanto-categoria-conceitual/> (accessed 18.10.2021).
- Musicultura, G. (2015) *É permitido proibir: a práxis sonora da pacificação*. Revista Vórtex, 3, 2: 149-158.
- Silva, F. M. & Silva, K. R. (2012). *O Novo Modelo de Segurança Pública no Rio de Janeiro: violação ou garantia de Direitos Humanos nas favelas cariocas?*. Pós Revista Brasiliense de Pós-Graduação em Ciências Sociais, 11(01), 38-62.
- Silva, Rogério de Souza (2012) *A periferia pede passagem: trajetória social e intelectual de Mano Brown*. (Tese de doutoramento em Sociologia, Instituto de Filosofia e Ciências Humanas, Universidade Estadual de Campinas).
- Zaluar, A., & Conceição, I. S. (2007). *Favelas sob o controle das milícias no Rio de Janeiro*. São Paulo em Perspectiva, 21(2), 89-101.
- Žižek, S. (1999). *The Ticklish Subject*. London: Verso.

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